

ammonium thiocyanate and 0.1 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was prepared in distilled water. Acetate buffer was used for adjustment of pH of the aqueous solution. Acidity was measured with an ECL 5651 digital pH meter.

A Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurement.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the cobalt(II) solution containing upto 300 μg of cobalt, ammonium thiocyanate (2 ml) and CTAB solutions (0.4 ml) were added. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml with acetate buffer and distilled water so that pH of the solution was maintained at 3.5 ± 0.5 . The resulting mixture was then shaken (30 s) with chloroform (10 ml). The separated blue organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water droplets. The absorbance of the chloroform extract was then measured at 625 nm against the reagent blank and the amount of cobalt estimated. To test the interference, foreign ions were added to the aqueous solution before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between cobalt(II), thiocyanate and CTAB was instantaneous. 1 ml of ammonium thiocyanate along with 0.2 ml of CTAB was sufficient to extract 135 μg of cobalt in a single operation. Higher concentrations of the reagent, however, did not bring about any significant change in the maximum value of absorbance.

A steady and maximum absorbance was obtained when the extractions were carried out throughout the entire range, i.e. from 4 M HCl medium to pH 8.0. In each case the remaining aqueous phase, after a single extraction, was void of cobalt as tested by an independent method. At 0.1 M sodium hydroxide medium, cobalt(II) showed no colour reaction with the reagents.

The $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{-SCN-CTAB}$ complex in chloroform exhibited absorption maxima at 625 nm with a shoulder around 585 nm. The reagent blank does not absorb in the aforesaid wavelength region. The pattern of the absorption spectrum of the complex, extracted throughout the entire range (4 M HCl medium to pH 8.0) remained unchanged. This indicates the existence of a single variety of the complex species in the system. The absorbance of the chloroform extract remained virtually constant for at least 96 h.

The absorbance of the blue complex in chloroform showed a linear response upto 30 ppm of cobalt. The molar absorptivity of the complex, based on cobalt content, was evaluated to be $1.92 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the corresponding Sandell's sensitivity of $0.031 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 625 nm.

Interference: In order to study the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, cobalt was extracted and determined according to the

recommended procedure in presence of the respective foreign ions. Extraction pH was set at 3.5 with acetate buffer, unless otherwise mentioned. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of cobalt differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken. Cobalt(II) (135 μg) could be determined without interference in presence of 50–60 fold excess of Be^{II} , Tl^{I} , Al^{III} , Th^{IV} , U^{VI} , Pt^{IV} , Rh^{III} , La^{III} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Bi^{III} , Pb^{II} , V^{V} , Ni^{II} , Ag^{I} , Zr^{IV} , Mg^{II} , Ce^{III} , Sn^{II} . The system tolerated 20–5 fold excess of Mo^{IV} and Fe^{III} (more than 50-fold excess in presence of ammonium hydrogenfluoride), and 5–10 fold excess of Pd^{II} . A 30-fold excess of Cd^{II} did not interfere if the extraction be carried out from 3 M HCl medium. In presence of Cu^{II} , the chloroform extract became hazy and absorption of the organic layer could not be measured, and this interference could not be removed. Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} must be absent as Co^{II} showed no colour reaction in their presence.

Among the anions tested, a 100-fold excess of thiosulphate, iodide, fluoride, phosphate, acetate, phthalate, tartrate, ascorbate, sulphate, and a 30-fold excess of citrate and oxalate did not have any effect. Extraction should be carried out from 3 M HCl medium to avoid the interference due to EDTA.

The proposed method was tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of cobalt. The average of six determinations of 135 μg Co was found to be 133 μg with the relative mean deviation of $\pm 1.3\%$.

Reference

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Extraction of Lead with a Liquid Anion Exchanger and its Application in Rat Tissue Samples

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IN the present paper we describe a method for selective quantitative extraction of trace quantities of lead as its complex with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) using the liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336 in cyclohexane and its subsequent determination by flame AAS. The method has been successfully applied to determine lead content in kidney and liver tissues of *Rattus norvegicus*.

Experimental

Liquid anion-exchanger Aliquat 336 (Fluka, A.G.) was used as such. The stock solution of lead(II) was prepared by dissolving lead nitrate (A.R.) in double-distilled water and standardised complexometrically¹. The solution of NTA (Sigma) was prepared in dilute sodium hydroxide solution. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

A Shimadzu AA-646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used having following conditions: lead hollow cathode lamp current, 7 mA; burner height, 5 mm; wavelength, 217.0 nm; slit width, 0.19 nm; air flow rate, 10 dm³ min⁻¹; acetylene flow rate, 2.6 dm³ min⁻¹. pH was measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

General procedure: To an aliquot of the stock solution containing 160 µg of lead, an excess of NTA solution was added. pH was adjusted to ~10.6 and borax buffer solution (pH 10.6; 2 ml) was then added. The resulting solution was transferred into a separatory funnel and shaken for 2 min with 5% Aliquat 336 (10 ml) dissolved in cyclohexane. The two layers were allowed to settle for about 10 min. The organic phase was taken into another separatory funnel and the aqueous phase was washed with cyclohexane (2 × 3 ml). The combined cyclohexane extract was stripped back with 0.1 M HClO₄ solution (2 × 4 ml). The combined aqueous phase was equilibrated with cyclohexane (5 ml) to remove any trace of Aliquat 336. Volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml with water. The absorbance of the solution was measured on the AAS against a reagent blank and the amount of lead determined.

TABLE 1 - DETERMINATION OF LEAD IN RAT TISSUE

Sample no.	Tissue	Amount taken (g)	Lead content* (µg g ⁻¹)	
			Present method	Direct AAS
1	Kidney	0.428 65	92.20 ± 0.32	83.37 ± 0.62
	Liver	2.706 00	18.18 ± 0.01	14.65 ± 0.21
2	Kidney	0.499 30	68.23 ± 0.27	60.19 ± 0.36
	Liver	2.965 75	12.85 ± 0.06	9.76 ± 0.15
3	Kidney	0.672 80	39.01 ± 0.16	31.62 ± 0.44
	Liver	2.897 00	5.18 ± 0.02	2.97 ± 0.29
4	Kidney	0.493 01	63.39 ± 0.25	58.84 ± 0.18
	Liver	2.727 05	4.96 ± 0.02	2.65 ± 0.20
5	Kidney	0.466 85	91.72 ± 0.38	85.81 ± 0.32
	Liver	2.100 75	9.54 ± 0.04	6.87 ± 0.24

*Average of 4 determinations.

Determination of lead in rat tissues: The whole kidney and liver were collected and treated² separately

from each of *Rattus norvegicus*. Known weight of the tissue samples were digested with concentrated HNO₃ (20–50 ml) by gently heating until foaming subsided. The solution was boiled with occasional additions of concentrated HNO₃ until it was clear brown. A few drops of 60% HClO₄ was then added and the resulting solution was heated till it was colourless. The volume of the solution was then made up to 25 ml with water. Lead content of the solution was then determined as per the procedure described above. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of parameters: The extraction of lead complex was found to reach a constant value over the pH range 10.5–10.8. The working pH was 10.6 and borax buffer was used to maintain the pH. Quantitative extraction (99.6%) of lead occurred with cyclohexane. The results with other solvents were as follows: chloroform, 59.7; n-butanol, 8.5; methyl isobutyl ketone, 46.9; benzene, 62.2; toluene, 61.9 and xylene, 64.8%. The extraction or back-extraction was completed within 2 min and 10 min to settle the equilibrium.

Interference: Separation of lead (16 µg) was carried out in presence of various ions within an error of ± 2%. The results are as follows (the ion concentration in µg is indicated in parenthesis): Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻ and SO₄²⁻ (5000); Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Fe³⁺ (1000); Cd²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, WO₄²⁻, VO₄³⁻, AsO₄³⁻, SO₃²⁻ and I⁻ (500); Zn²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Cu²⁺ (400); Al³⁺, SCN⁻, PO₄³⁻ (100); S₂O₈²⁻, S²⁻ (50). The separation of lead (16 µg) was possible in the presence of more than one foreign ion (in µg) in the following mixtures (within an error of not more than ± 2%): (i) Ca²⁺ (500) + Mg²⁺ (500) + Zn²⁺ (100); (ii) Mn²⁺ (500) + Fe³⁺ (500) + Al³⁺ (100); (iii) WO₄²⁻ (500) + VO₄³⁻ (500) + AsO₄³⁻ (500); (iv) I⁻ (500) + SO₄²⁻ (500) + PO₄³⁻ (100); (v) Cu²⁺ (100) + Cd²⁺ (100) + Hg²⁺ (100).

TABLE 2 - RECOVERY OF LEAD IN RAT TISSUE SAMPLE NO. 2

Sample no.	Lead (µg)		
	Amount added	Amount found	% Recovery
Kidney	—	1.36*	—
	10.00	11.16	98.0
	12.50	13.92	101.5
	15.00	16.32	99.7
Liver	—	1.52*	—
	10.00	11.72	102.0
	12.50	14.40	103.0
	15.00	16.72	101.3

*In 1.0 ml of the solution aliquot.

The amount of lead found in kidney was always higher than that in liver (Table 1) and the values

are below the LD_{50} (rat) = $150 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ value^a. The wet digested solutions of the tissues after spiked with lead were estimated by the proposed method. The results obtained for the recovery of lead in sample no. 2 (Table 1) have been presented in Table 2.

Direct analysis of the tissue samples gave lower results than the present method. The analytical recovery of lead (Table 2) indicates reliability of the proposed method.

Nature of extracted species: The extraction of $\text{Pb}(\text{NTA})_2^{4-}$ was quantitative provided the molar-ratio of Aliquat 336: lead was ≥ 4 . Plot of $\log D$ vs $\log [\text{Aliquat 336}]$ was a straight line with slope of 4.1, which suggests the equilibrium,

where o is the organic phase, a the aqueous phase and R_4N^+ is Aliquat 336.

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References

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